

Spin-Wave Nanoscale RF Delay Lines for Mid and High Frequency 5G Band

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Delay lines (DL) are crucial components in communication systems, providing the required time delays for signal timing, synchronization, and processing. DLs providing nanosecond-scale delays are conventionally based on acoustic waves; however, they cannot operate conveniently in a high-frequency range (EU 5G high-band 24.25 – 27.5 GHz) required by a modern generation of 5G communication technologies to speed up data transfer. The proposed solution is to use DL based on spin-wave (SW) transmission, as SW devices allow for operation at high-frequency ranges and can be scaled down to a few μm^2 . In this study, we investigate SW-based DL at the nanoscale at the frequency ranges of 4 GHz, 9 GHz, and 25 GHz. The DL is based on SW transmission between a pair of 250 nm wide microwave coplanar waveguide (CPW) transducers, each with a footprint of $2.25 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$, and fabricated with varying mutual distances on a 97 nm thin yttrium iron garnet (YIG) film. DLs are tested for in-plane SW modes (Damon-Eshbach and Backward Volume), and depending on the parameters, the extracted delay times are in the range of 6 – 165 ns. Time-gating analysis of the measured transmission is performed, providing a detailed discussion of individual signal contributions to the measured spectra. Additionally, analytical theory is employed to compare the experimental delay times with analytical calculations and to predict how to adjust the device parameters to obtain variable time delays.

I. MOTIVATION

Communication systems urgently need to speed up data transfer due to the increasing number of active user devices every year [1]. Therefore, the aim of modern 5G technology systems is to move from standard frequency ranges (e.g., EU 5G low-band 694 – 790 MHz and mid-band 3.4–3.8 GHz) to high-frequency ranges (e.g., EU 5G high-band 24.25 – 27.5 GHz). However, moving to higher frequency ranges is challenging for many radio-frequency (RF) devices, such as filters, limiters, and delay lines that are conventionally used at lower frequency ranges [2].

Delay lines (DLs) are two-port devices that delay signal transmission by a fixed amount of time to synchronize signals. This is crucial for error reduction in signal processing, timing, and phase shifting, especially in multi-band and multi-antenna systems used in modern 5G communication systems [2].

In telecommunication systems, either photonic or acoustic DLs are conventionally used for on-chip signal processing applications. DLs based on photonic integrated circuits (PICs) [3–7] leverage the propagation of light through optical waveguides and offer several advantages, including broadband operation, performance up to THz frequency range, and small insertion losses. However, since on-chip PIC-based DLs provide delay times in the ps range, it remains challenging to simultaneously

achieve tunability, longer delay times (at ns range), and a small device footprint [3, 4].

The synchronisation requirements and delay compensations needed for 5G networks are from picoseconds to a few hundred nanoseconds [8, 9].

Therefore, searching for a technology providing longer delay times is of interest. One of the suitable candidates are acoustic DLs based either on surface acoustic waves (SAWs) [10–16] or on bulk acoustic waves (BAWs) [17–20]. SAW-based DLs can provide delay times in the range of a few ns up to several hundred ns. However, they can operate conveniently only in the low GHz range (approx. up to 3 GHz [10]) because of the significantly increasing damping of acoustic waves with increasing frequency, resulting in high insertion losses [11]. Additionally, operating SAW DLs at higher frequencies requires proportionally smaller interdigitated transducers (IDTs), which poses significant challenges for conventional optical lithography techniques used for their fabrication [12]. Compared to SAW-based DLs, BAW-based DLs can provide significantly longer delay times in the range of a few hundred ns up to several hundred ms, and they can also operate at slightly higher frequency ranges (up to approximately 6 GHz [21]). However, BAW-based DLs suffer from complicated fabrication due to the high requirements for BAW isolation from the substrate and increasing damping with increasing frequency [12].

Therefore, it is of interest for the next generation of communication technology to search for a DL capable of operating in the high frequency range (around 25 GHz) and simultaneously providing longer delay times (in the ns range). One possible solution can be DLs based on spin-wave (SW) transmission, as they allow effective operation at high-frequency ranges with provided delay times in the ns range. Moreover, SW-based DLs are frequency flexible (the same device can operate at any frequency range defined by the external magnetic field), are easy to fabricate, and allow for device miniaturization [2, 22]. Additionally, SW-based devices provide multifunctionality, meaning that a single SW device can simultaneously work as a delay line, filter, and power limiter [22]. Furthermore, the delay time can be precisely tuned by the choice of the magnetic material (sample thickness, saturation magnetization), antenna design (mutual distance between the antennas), and applied magnetic field, determining the frequency range and SW mode [23–27]. However, in the past, SW-based DLs have been investigated only at the macroscale [28–34], in the centimeter and millimeter ranges, and in the low-frequency ranges (up to 5 GHz).

In this study, we investigate nanoscale DLs based on the spin-wave transmission between a pair of 250 nm wide coplanar microwave (CPW) transducers, each with a footprint of $2.25 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$, of different mutual center-to-center spacings, which are fabricated on the 97 nm thin yttrium iron garnet (YIG) film. The DLs are tested in a broad frequency range of 4 GHz, 9 GHz, and 25 GHz for both in-plane SW modes - Damon-Eshbach (DE, applied field is perpendicular to the SW propagation) and Backward Volume (BV, applied field is parallel to SW propagation). To extract the delay time, a time-gating analysis of the measured SW transmission is performed, providing a detailed discussion of the various signal contributions, including electromagnetic leakage, and explaining the oscillations in the measured SW spectra. The extracted delay times are compared with analytical calculations, and the possibility of obtaining variable delay times by tuning the device parameters (such as sample thickness, or using different SW modes) is discussed.

II. NANOSCALE SW-BASED DELAY LINES

The DL devices consist of CPW transducers and a magnetic film. As a magnetic medium, the 97 nm thin liquid phase epitaxy (LPE) grown YIG film on (111) gallium gadolinium garnet (GGG) is used because of favorable damping characteristics [35], resulting in long propagation distances of spin waves. On top of the YIG layer, the microwave transducers are fabricated using PMMA resist and e-beam lithography, followed by metal evaporation (10 nm Ti, 320 nm Cu, 20 nm Au) and lift-off. The fabricated transducers consist of three fingers,

each 250 nm wide with 750 nm spacing, and a length of 100 μm . The center-to-center distance between the transducers is 3 μm , 7.5 μm and 52.5 μm , and their total thickness is 350 nm; see Fig. 1.

FIG. 1. SEM images of SW-based DLs consisting of microwave transducers on the YIG film. The lengths of the transducers are 100 μm , and both signal (S) and ground (G) conductors are 250 nm wide and 750 nm apart from each other. The center-to-center distance D between the transducers is (a) $D = 3 \mu\text{m}$, (b) $D = 7.5 \mu\text{m}$, and (c) $D = 52.5 \mu\text{m}$. Spin-wave propagation between the input and output transducers and the signal conversion between electromagnetic (EM) and spin-wave (SW) signals are indicated in (c).

The microwave transducers are connected via pico-probes and coaxial cables to the vector network analyzer (VNA), which generates and detects microwave signals (electromagnetic waves, EM). For characterization of DLs, propagating spin-wave spectroscopy (PSWS) [22, 36, 37] is used. The principle is the following: the DL device is located in the external magnetic field, and the microwave current generated by the VNA is sent to the input transducer. The microwave current creates an alternating magnetic field around the transducer, which interacts with the magnetic moments in the magnetic layer beneath. If the frequency of the microwave current matches the SW dispersion relation (determined by the external magnetic field and material parameters), spin waves are generated, and they propagate in the magnetic film. When they reach the output transducer, the alternating magnetic field (created by magnetic moment precession) induces a voltage in the output transducer, which is detected by the VNA. The transmitted SW signal can be represented by the scattering parameter S_{21} , which is the ratio of the detected and generated signals.

The time delay T_d is determined by the SW group

velocity v_g and the distance D between the transducers

$$T_d = \frac{D}{v_g}. \quad (1)$$

The SW group velocity is a derivative of the SW dispersion relation

$$v_g = \frac{2\pi\partial f}{\partial k}, \quad (2)$$

which is calculated from the analytical model of Kalinikos and Slavin [38], using these input values: saturation magnetization $M_s = 140$ kA/m, gyromagnetic ratio $\gamma/2\pi = 28$ GHz/T, film thickness $t = 97$ nm, exchange constant $A_{\text{ex}} = 3.6$ pJ/m. The spin-wave mode and applied magnetic field used in the calculations are summarized in Table I.

III. MEASUREMENTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

We characterize the fabricated DLs described in the previous section using the time-gating analysis [39–43]. SW transmission is measured using VNA in the frequency domain [22, 36, 37, 39, 44, 45], and then the inverse Fourier transform (IFT) is applied to convert the measured data into the time domain. This emulates propagation of a very short pulse (with the duration being the inverse frequency band accounted for in the calculations - see the appendix) and allows for distinguishing all the possible contributions to the transmission. The analysis of a finite-length pulse propagation is discussed later. In the time domain, we identify and extract the signal of interest, a peak whose amplitude corresponds to a specific delay time T_d . To gain deeper insight into the time domain data, the Fourier transform (FT) of the signal of interest (extracted peak with annulled surroundings) is applied to convert this signal back to the frequency domain for comparison with the original data. This time-gating analysis enables the identification of the individual signal contributions and their origin in the measured transmission, allowing for further optimization of SW devices by eliminating unwanted signal components. Please note that the time-gating analysis is applicable only to time-invariant linear systems.

Moreover, in many cases, the SW signal in the measured transmission is very weak, particularly in a few-nanometer-thick structured YIG films. The standard procedure to eliminate parasitic signals (e.g., electromagnetic leakage) typically involves subtracting the reference transmission (measured at different magnetic fields) from the transmission of interest, which is both time-consuming and prone to inaccuracies. Compared to this standard method of background subtraction, time-gating is highly efficient in finding the signal of interest in the measured transmission spectrum in the frequency domain.

The time-gating analysis of all signal contributions in the transmission spectra measured using transducers with a distance of $7.5 \mu\text{m}$, in the DE mode, is shown in Fig. 2. The measured SW transmission in the frequency domain (original raw data) at 3–5 GHz is plotted in gray in the first row in Fig. 2(a). The IFT of the measured (raw) data in the time domain is also plotted in gray in the second row. The signal of interest in the time domain is highlighted in color for each column, and its FT is plotted in the same color in the frequency domain. In the following text, the individual signal contributions in Fig. 2(a) are described.

- *The first column I.* The fastest signal that is detected by the second VNA port is the **electromagnetic leakage**, i.e., the crosstalk between the transducers [46]. The electromagnetic leakage creates the background in the frequency domain, and it is of interest to reduce it as much as possible to have the best signal-to-noise ratio for the SW signal.
- *The second column II.* After the electromagnetic leakage, the main **SW signal** takes place. Compared to electromagnetic leakage, the SW signal is slower as it propagates at a speed of the SW group velocity (in this case $v_g = 598$ m/s) from the input to the output transducer. This propagation defines the delay time T_d , which is extracted from the measured data as $T_d = 13.6 \pm 3.2$ ns. The theoretical delay time T_d^* , determined by the distance between the transducers and the SW group velocity (see Eq. 1), is $T_d^* = 12.5$ ns, and agrees well with the experimental one. The SW signal maximum (-27 dB) is 29 dB larger than the median value of the electromagnetic leakage (-56 dB) extracted at the frequency range of the SW signal (3.8 – 4.3 GHz).
- *The third column III.* The next signal contribution appears as an **interference of two signals**. We see a pronounced beating in the time domain with a period $\Delta T \approx 2$ ns, as evidenced in the zoomed-in signal profile Fig. 2(d). The reconstructed spectrum of this signal of interest contains two peaks, one at the same frequency position as the main SW peak discussed just above (around 4 GHz) and the second at about 4.5 GHz. Frequency separation between the peaks $\Delta f \approx 0.5$ GHz gives the period of beating in the time domain $\Delta T = 1/\Delta f$. These two peaks are both SW peaks. The shape and size of the transducer used for SW generation, together with the SW dispersion relation, determine the wavenumbers k of the generated spin waves. The excitation spectra J_{exc} of the transducer (blue curve in Fig. 2(c)) are calculated as a Fourier transform of the normalized current density in the trans-

ducer [22, 36]. The main SW signal contribution in the measured data is from the first peak in the excitation spectra at $k = 3.1 \text{ rad}/\mu\text{m}$ (wavelength $\lambda = 2.026 \mu\text{m}$), and the side contribution is from the second peak $k_s = 9.3 \text{ rad}/\mu\text{m}$ ($\lambda_s = 0.675 \mu\text{m}$). The intersection of the excitation spectra with the dispersion relation (black curve in Fig. 2(c)) determines the SW frequency range in the measured transmission (gray curve in Fig. 2(c)). The SW group velocities differ within the main peak ($v_g = 598 \text{ m/s}$) and side peak ($v_{g,s} = 316 \text{ m/s}$). Theoretical delay for shorter SW (secondary peak) is $T_{d,s}^* = D/v_{g,s} = 23.8 \text{ ns}$, close to the measured one $T_d = 29.5 \pm 4.5 \text{ ns}$. Thus, the signal from the second peak in the excitation spectra is the SW signal at a smaller wavelength that propagates as a common one-way from the excitation towards the detection transducer. The nature of the signal at the main excitation peak is more nontrivial. To match theoretical delay time with the experimental one, we need to assume that the signal propagates the doubled distance, i.e., $T_d^* = 2D/v_g = 25.0 \text{ ns}$. Thus, the signal from the first peak of the excitation spectra originates from the SWs that travel from the excitation transducer towards the detection transducer and back. We assume that this signal contribution is present in the measured transmission due to the interference of this reflected SW signal with the electromagnetic leakage signal that is being generated at the emitting transducer and detected at the output, as we are operating at the continuous-wave (CW) mode. Because the two aforementioned delay times are similar, the interference occurs, see Fig. 2(d). Both discussed contributions are weak compared to the main SW peak (column II) – 24.5 dB smaller for the second excitation peak contribution and 28.2 dB smaller for the double reflected signal.

- *The fourth and the fifth columns IV. and V.* In the fourth and fifth columns, **the SW signals with two and three reflections from the transducers** are highlighted. Its theoretical delay times $T_d^* = 3D/v_g = 37.5 \text{ ns}$ and $T_d^* = 4D/v_g = 50.0 \text{ ns}$ agree reasonably with the experimental one $T_d = 41.0 \pm 5.2 \text{ ns}$ and $T_d = 53.0 \pm 3.1 \text{ ns}$. The differences between the contributions from the signals with two reflections (–48 dB) and three reflections (–61 dB) from the transducers are 21 dB and 24 dB compared to the main SW signal maximum (–27 dB). We assume that, also in this case, the SW signal with three reflections is present in the measured transmission due to the interference with the electromagnetic leakage when reaching the emitting transducer.

Based on this analysis, the main SW signal exceeds the electromagnetic leakage by 29 dB, the side peak from the second excitation maxima by 24.5 dB, and the contribution from two reflections on the transducers by 21 dB. Therefore, despite the presence of these parasitic signals, the DL performance remains good, with a margin exceeding 20 dB.

Moreover, this time-gating analysis is particularly useful for understanding the original data measured in the frequency domain (in gray). Both the main and the side SW signals exhibit some oscillations; see Fig. 2(b). These oscillations are caused by the interference of two signals. To explain their origin, an IFT must be performed simultaneously for two signals of interest with an annulled background.

The oscillations present in the main SW peak are obtained when the IFT is calculated from the SW signal that propagates once between the transducers and the SW signal that travels three times back and forth between the transducers. Both of these signal contributions in the time domain are highlighted in light green in Fig. 2(b). For certain applications, such as SW-based filters, it is crucial to minimize these oscillations to achieve a well-defined peak shape, ideally as close as possible to a rectangular profile. These oscillations can be minimized by introducing an insulation layer between the YIG film and the transducers, as they originate from SW reflection at the interface between the metal transducers and the YIG film. There is a trade-off in the insulation layer thickness; the thicker the layer, the more suppressed the SW reflections, but the SW excitation and detection efficiency drop because the transducers are further away from the YIG film.

The oscillations in the side peak are caused by interference of the SW signal from the second peak in the excitation spectrum and electromagnetic leakage, as highlighted in dark green in Fig. 2(b). The electromagnetic leakage interferes with all the signals, but pronounced oscillations in the SW signal peaks are present only when the SW signal is comparable to or smaller in magnitude than the electromagnetic leakage. Therefore, for SW devices, it is crucial to minimize electromagnetic leakage as much as possible, thus achieving a better signal-to-noise ratio and avoiding unwanted oscillations in the signal of interest. Electromagnetic leakage can be minimized by optimizing the transducer design, particularly the transducer pads to contact the picoprobes.

A real device is operating with finite-length pulses (units up to tens of nanoseconds) that have relatively narrow frequency spectra rather than a wide uniform spectrum in the whole measurement band (which mimics in our case a pulse of just 0.5 ns length, as we take 2 GHz band into consideration). To analyze transmission of such pulses, we consider a normalized 10 ns long Gaussian pulse at the carrier frequency of 4.1 GHz (see Fig. 2(e)). The calculations are done in a standard

FIG. 2. (a) *In grey, the upper row:* Measured spin-wave (SW) transmission using the transducers with center-to-center distance of $D = 7.5 \mu\text{m}$, at Damon-Eshbach configuration and with the input power of -30 dBm , bandwidth 1 kHz , frequency step 200 kHz , no averaging, and applied field of 71 mT . *in grey, the lower row:* The IFT of the measured SW transmission to the time domain. *in color:* The signal of interest in the time domain is highlighted in color, and its FT with the annulled background back to the frequency domain is highlighted in the same color. *in columns:* The individual signal contributions are highlighted and compared to the original data in each column. There are three different signals - the electromagnetic leakage (the curved arrow in I.), the SW signal with small wavenumbers that undergo reflections from the transducers (straight arrows in II., III., IV., and V.), and the SW signal with large wavenumbers (double-arrow in III.), detailed description is provided in the text. (b) The interference of two signals causes the oscillations in the measured SW transmission (in grey). The signal contributions in the time domain are highlighted in light green for the main SW peak and in dark green for the side SW peak. (c) The SW transmission (in grey) occurs at the frequency range that matches the intersection of the SW dispersion relation (in black) and the transducer excitation efficiency (in blue). The arrows symbolizing the individual signal contributions in (a) are assigned to the first and second peaks in the excitation spectra. (d) The details of the interference of two SW signals with different wavenumbers in the time domain in III. The distance between two maxima in the time domain (2 ns) corresponds to the distance in frequency between the main and the side SW signal, as highlighted in dark cyan in (c). (e) Normalised, 10 ns long, Gaussian pulse in the time domain. (f) Gaussian pulse in the frequency domain (in blue), and the measured SW transmission (in grey). (g) Comparison of the measured SW transmission (in grey) and the measured SW transmission multiplied by the Gaussian pulse in the frequency domain (in dark blue). (h) The IFT of the measured SW transmission (in grey) and of the measured SW transmission multiplied by the Gaussian pulse (in dark blue) to the time domain.

FIG. 3. (a) *In gray* Measured spin-wave (SW) transmission using the transducers with center-to-center distance of 3 μm (first row), 7.5 μm (second row) and 52.5 μm (third row). The SW transmission is measured at 4 GHz, 9 GHz, and 25 GHz with a frequency span of 2 GHz for both Damon-Eshbach (DE) and Backward Volume (BV) modes. The VNA parameters used: power -30 dBm, bandwidth 1 kHz, frequency step 200 kHz, and no averaging. The applied magnetic fields are depicted in Table I. *In color* the Fourier transform of the signal of interest with annulled surroundings in the time domain in (b) back to the frequency domain (highlighted in color, green for DE and red for BV). (b) *In gray* The inverse Fourier transform of the measured SW transmission in (a) to the time domain. The SW amplitude in the time domain is normalized for better signal visibility. *In color* The signal of interest (SW signal) is highlighted in color. The time delay T_d is extracted at the SW signal maxima or in the middle of the peak when multiple maxima are present.

way – the pulse frequency spectrum (light blue curve in Fig. 2(f)) is multiplied by the amplitude-frequency characteristics of the delay line, which is nothing else than the measured frequency-dependent SW transmission in continuous mode (grey curve in Fig. 2(f)). The resulting spectrum of the transmitted signal (dark blue curve in Fig. 2(g)) is then converted back to the time domain using IFT, where it is compared with the original data; see Fig. 2(h).

From this comparison, it is visible that the second peak (at about 30 ns delay) is more suppressed, since the second excitation maximum in the antenna spectrum does not contribute to the transmission now – its separation from the main peak overcomes the signal bandwidth. Os-

cillations of the transmitted signal are also suppressed for the same reason. Other peaks, with a delay of about 41 ns and 53 ns, are still there, meaning that these peaks originate from the SW signal that undergoes multiple reflections. At the same time, these side peaks are at least 10 times in amplitude (i.e., 20 dB) smaller than the main one. In addition, the main peak distortions and dispersion spreading are weak. These two features prove that the SW-based DL is able to operate in the ns-pulse regime, preserving the well-defined pulse structure and delay time.

To construct an effective SW-based DL, it is essential to suppress both electromagnetic leakage and signals arising from SW reflections at the transducers. The desired

signal for DL application is the SW signal from the main peak, which propagates only one-way from the excitation to the detection transducer, and is more than 20 dB larger than the other contributions. In the following text, we focus solely on this main SW signal.

We performed systematic measurements using the fabricated DLs with different center-to-center distances between the transducers. The measured SW transmissions for both SW modes and all investigated frequency ranges are plotted in gray in Fig. 3(a). The IFT of the measured SW transmission to the time domain is also plotted in gray in Fig. 3(b). The signal of interest in the time domain is highlighted in color (green for DE and red for BV). The FT of this signal is plotted in the same color in the frequency domain in Fig. 3(a). The signal of interest is the main SW signal that propagates from the excitation transducer towards the detection transducer. It is a pure SW signal with no electromagnetic leakage and no contributions from other SW signals, such as the reflected ones or those with different wavelengths. The delay time T_d is extracted from the normalized SW amplitude either at the peak maximum (most cases) or in the middle of the peak, when multiple maxima are present. The signal amplitude in the time domain is normalized to the maximum signal for better peak visibility.

This analysis, shown in Fig. 3(b), clearly demonstrates that SW-based nanoscale DLs work in the broad frequency range up to 25 GHz, providing different delay times depending on the transducer distance and SW mode. The insertion losses of the presented DL devices are higher than 20 dB; however, if the DL device would be used at a single frequency, the signal demonstrates a 20 dB margin over the background. The insertion losses can be significantly decreased, potentially down to 3 dB [2], by increasing the thickness of the YIG film and by optimizing the transducer [47–50].

FIG. 4. The experimental delay time (solid line) extracted from Fig. 3(b) and the theoretical delay (dashed line) time calculated using Eq. 1 for Damon-Eshbach (DE, in green) and Backward Volume (BV, in red) and for different distances between the transducers of 3 μm , 7.5 μm , and 52.5 μm .

The comparison of the SW delay time in the time domain for both SW modes is shown in Fig. 4. The delay times are extracted from the measurements in Fig. 3(b) for all investigated frequency ranges and SW modes, except the DE mode at 25 GHz, as no SW signal was found in the time domain spectrum. The experimental delay times are compared with the theoretical delay times obtained from analytical calculations using the Kalinikos-Slavin [38] model, as described above. The applied magnetic fields used in the calculations, together with the group velocities, calculated using Eq. 2, and extracted at $k = 3.1 \text{ rad}/\mu\text{m}$, are depicted in Tab. I. The theoretical delay times T_d^* , calculated using the corresponding group velocity and transducer distance (Eq. 1), and the experimental delay times T_d are depicted in Tab. I for all investigated distances D between transducers, frequency ranges, and SW modes.

From Fig. 4(a) and Tab. I is visible that the analytical calculations agree well with the delay times extracted from the measurements. As expected, the larger the distance between the transducers, the longer the delay time and the smaller the SW amplitude due to damping during SW propagation. With increasing frequency, the delay time increases for DE and decreases for BV. This is because the group velocity increases for DE and decreases for BV with increasing frequency; see Table I.

IV. DISCUSSION

As there is a good match between the experimental results and the analytical theory, the theory can be implemented to predict and optimize the DL parameters to achieve specific delay times.

- **To achieve shorter delay times**, the simplest approach is to position the transducers as close to each other as possible; see Fig. 4(a). However, this approach has practical limitations, making it essential to explore strategies to maximize the SW group velocity. For spin waves with small wavenumbers, the group velocity increases with both the magnetic film thickness and the saturation magnetization. Doubling the thickness of the magnetic film results in an approximately twofold higher SW group velocity, thereby reducing the delay time by half. The only drawback is the increase in bulkiness of the device. The saturation magnetization of single-crystalline YIG films can be increased by substituting Nd and Pr ions; however, such substitutions drastically increase the damping. A more effective approach is the replacement of the iron ions on the octahedral lattice sites with diamagnetic ions such as Sc and In [51, 52]. Another approach can be to use magnetic materials with higher damping, such as nanocrystalline YIG films, whose magne-

TABLE I. The applied magnetic field B , calculated group velocities v_g at $k = 3.1 \text{ rad}/\mu\text{m}$, theoretical T_d^* and experimental T_d delay times for transducers with center-to-center distances of $3 \mu\text{m}$, $7.5 \mu\text{m}$, and $52.5 \mu\text{m}$, for Damon-Eshbach (DE) and Backward Volume (BV) modes at 4 GHz, 9 GHz and 25 GHz.

D (μm)		4 GHz		9 GHz		25 GHz	
		DE	BV	DE	BV	DE	BV
	B (mT)	71	87	244	255	807	823
	v_g (m/s)	597.8	307.6	297.9	428.5	144.6	507.8
3	T_d^* (ns)	5.0	9.8	10.1	7.0	20.8	5.9
	T_d (ns)	6.0 ± 2.0	8.6 ± 4.0	9.7 ± 3.5	7.3 ± 2.7	12.7 ± 8.5	6.5 ± 2.2
7.5	T_d^* (ns)	12.5	24.4	25.2	17.5	51.9	14.8
	T_d (ns)	13.6 ± 3.2	24.5 ± 7.3	26.7 ± 4.8	18.2 ± 3.5	42.9 ± 5.4	15.1 ± 2.9
52.5	T_d^* (ns)	87.8	170.7	176.3	122.5	363.2	103.4
	T_d (ns)	82.0 ± 14.1	165.3 ± 21.8	158.4 ± 14.9	111.5 ± 16.7	–	95.0 ± 9.8

tization can be increased by doping with rare earth ions [53] or using different magnetic materials with higher saturation magnetization, such as CoFeB or NiFe. However, this would lead to a decrease in signal magnitude as a result of the enhanced damping compared to the single-crystalline YIG films. Nevertheless, this effect might be less pronounced when the propagation distance between the transducers is very small. To further increase the group velocity, it is preferable to use the DE mode when operating in a lower frequency range and to use the BV mode in a higher frequency range; see Fig. 4(a), which agrees well with the results obtained in [22]. An option to increase the SW group velocity for the DE mode is to add a metalized surface to the YIG film [30].

- **To achieve longer delay times**, there are two solutions: (i) to place the transducers further away from each other (see Fig. 4(a)) or (ii) to operate at a lower SW group velocity. Both the solutions inevitably lead to a decrease in the SW amplitude (i.e. increased insertion losses), as it is determined by the delay-to-damping ratio; thus low-damping YIG becomes even more preferential for long-delay DLs. The solution (ii) benefits from a smaller device sizes and appears to be more preferential. Lower SW group velocity can be achieved by a choice of the SW mode, as already discussed above, or by restricting the YIG film to multiple waveguides (if operating at small SW wavenumbers). The SW group velocity can also be tuned by the shape and size of the transducers, determining the SW wavenumber (the narrower the transducer, the higher wavenumbers can be excited). The dispersion relation is usually the steepest for the dipolar spin waves (the region with the smallest wavenumbers) and for exchange spin waves (the region with high SW wavenumbers), leading to large group velocities. However, when operating in between these two regions at dipolar-exchange spin

waves, the group velocity can be very small, providing very long delay times. Another approach to lower the SW group velocity is to reduce the saturation magnetization of the YIG films by substituting diamagnetic ions, such as Ga or Al ions, for iron ions on the tetrahedral sublattice [54].

- **To achieve the dynamical adjustment of the SW DLs**, it is possible to tune their frequency range by the magnitude of an applied field, and their delay time by the direction of an applied field (i.e. operate at DE, BV or at any other spin-wave mode) [2].
- **To achieve small insertion losses and a good signal-to-noise ratio of the SW DL**, it is necessary to decrease the electromagnetic leakage and enhance SW excitation and detection efficiency. Both can be done by optimizing the transducer design and increasing the thickness of the YIG film [47–50, 55–57].

V. CONCLUSION

In summary, we report on the first study of the nanoscale DL based on SW transmission in the 97 nm thin YIG film. Three different DL devices are fabricated and tested, consisting of a pair of 250 nm wide transducers, each with a footprint of $2.25 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$, with center-to-center distances of $3 \mu\text{m}$, $7.5 \mu\text{m}$, and $52.5 \mu\text{m}$. The DLs are tested in the frequency range up to 25 GHz for the in-plane SW modes, DE, and BV, and their delay times are extracted by time-gating analysis. The shortest and longest delay times obtained at 25 GHz are $6.5 \pm 2.2 \text{ ns}$ and $95.0 \pm 9.8 \text{ ns}$ using the DLs with the smallest and largest distances of $3 \mu\text{m}$ and $52.5 \mu\text{m}$ and operating in BV mode. The measured delay times are compared with analytical calculations, which are employed to discuss variable delay times in future devices.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this article are openly available [58].

APPENDIX

Time-Domain Interpretation of VNA Measurements

Although a vector network analyzer (VNA) operates entirely in the frequency domain, it is possible to extract time-domain information from its data by performing an inverse Fourier transform (IFT) of the measured transmission coefficient $S_{21}(f)$. This transformation yields the system’s impulse response, which corresponds to the output signal that would result from a hypothetical input pulse.

The time-domain response obtained via IFT does not correspond to the response to an ideal Dirac delta pulse, but rather to a band-limited version of it. This is because the VNA only measures a finite frequency span $\Delta f = f_{\max} - f_{\min}$, and with a finite frequency resolution δf .

Input Pulse Shape

Assuming that the system is excited by a signal with constant amplitude across the measured frequency range

and zero elsewhere, the frequency-domain representation of the hypothetical input pulse is

$$G_{\text{pulse}}(f) = \begin{cases} 1, & f_{\min} \leq f \leq f_{\max} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The corresponding time-domain signal is obtained via the inverse Fourier transform:

$$\begin{aligned} g_{\text{pulse}}(t) &= \int_{f_{\min}}^{f_{\max}} e^{2\pi i f t} df \\ &= \frac{\sin[\pi \Delta f (t - t_0)]}{\pi(t - t_0)} \cdot e^{2\pi i f_c (t - t_0)} \\ &= \text{sinc}(\Delta f \cdot (t - t_0)) \cdot e^{2\pi i f_c (t - t_0)} \end{aligned}$$

where $f_c = \frac{f_{\min} + f_{\max}}{2}$ is the center frequency and $\text{sinc}(x) = \frac{\sin(\pi x)}{\pi x}$ is the normalized sinc function. The signal $g_{\text{pulse}}(t)$ is thus a band-limited sinc pulse modulated by the center frequency f_c .

Time Resolution and Window

The finite frequency span Δf determines the time resolution:

$$\Delta t \approx \frac{1}{\Delta f}$$

In practice, for a VNA measurement from 3 GHz to 5 GHz ($\Delta f = 2$ GHz), the time resolution is approximately $\Delta t = 0.5$ ns.

The total observable time window T is set by the frequency step size δf :

$$T = \frac{1}{\delta f}$$

For example, with a frequency step of $\delta f = 200$ kHz, the time window is $T = 5$ μ s, meaning the IFT will yield the impulse response sampled over this interval.

Interpretation of the Time-Domain Result

The time-domain response obtained from the IFT represents the system’s response to the sinc-like input pulse $g_{\text{pulse}}(t)$. Peaks in this response correspond to physical events such as direct electromagnetic coupling, spin-wave transmission, or reflections. The time of arrival of each peak provides a direct measurement of the time delay associated with each signal path.

This method, commonly referred to as *time-gating*, enables the isolation of distinct signal contributions in time

and allows for precise extraction of spin-wave group velocities and delay times without requiring direct time-domain excitation.

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